

EFFECT OF ARAMID FIBER CLOTH ON CARBON/ARAMID FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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Keywords: Carbon-fiber paper reinforced thermoplastics, Aramid cloth, Hybrid composites

ABSTRACT

Carbon-fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are well-known for their lightweight, outstanding strength and stiffness. Among them, carbon-fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) have attracted much attention because their mechanical performance is comparable to other counterparts and easier to be recycled and reused compared with carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting plastics (CFRTS). However, CFRTP's brittle failure behavior restricts their further application to various fields. One of the methods to improve the toughness is to manufacture hybrid composites. By hybridizing with ductile fibers, the toughness of CFRTP would be improved and a better general performance can be achieved by positive hybrid effect. In this study, to investigate the hybrid effect on CFRTP, carbon fiber paper and two kinds of continuous aramid fabric cloths with different bundle thicknesses, M0200s and M1000s, were used and the interlayer hybrids were manufactured. Static tests—tensile test, three-point bending test and dynamic tests—three-point impact test, Izod test were carried out in this study. Carbon/glass fiber hybridized thermoplastic was also manufactured with the same volume ratio and stacking sequence to compare with carbon/aramid fiber hybrids. It was found that there is toughness improvement in hybrids with aramid cloths. In addition, the aramid fabric with a thicker bundle showed a larger reinforcement effect in three-point bending test. And the positive hybrid effect was more obvious in dynamic loading where the energy absorption ability of carbon/aramid hybrids showed several times higher than that of carbon fiber paper reinforced thermoplastic itself.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastic materials have been more and more applied in broad areas with an expectation to improve the energy utilization efficiency due to their outstanding low density. Among them, Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are attracting much attention by showing high mechanical performances with much lighter weight in comparison with metallic materials. In particular, they are attempted to be applied as the car body to moderate global warming by reducing CO₂ emission. Basically, there are two types of CFRP —Carbon-fiber reinforced thermosetting plastics (CFRTS) and Carbon-fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP). CFRTP consist of carbon fiber and thermoplastics, which can be molded to other shapes again by getting soft repeatedly under the temperature about 200°C. For this reason, compared to CFRTS, CFRTP are more attractive because they take less time to mold and are suited to complex shape part molding. These advantages make it easier to repair or recycle them and have potential in mass production industries. In the case that a lot of CFRTP are recycled in the market, CFRTP made with recycled short carbon fibers would increase. They are called discontinuous CFRTP and have high fluidity, which is further desirable to mold complex shapes. However, CFRP lack their toughness and this defect is more obvious in discontinuous CFRTP, which is a critical disadvantage as the engineer materials. They are often related to limited failure strain caused by their instantaneous failure. Failure happens without distinguishing warnings in advance, which is unwanted for the safety sector and further application is limited. Some researchers have been tried to improve their toughness and moderate the abrupt failure mode. Applying the hybrid is the major as one of the ways to reinforce CFRTP toughness. The hybrid is a mixture of multiple materials and this is expected to improve the defects of the reference materials and have balanced performance [1-4]. There are several types of hybrid structures; interlayer and intralayer are famous types of them [5]. In this study, the interlayer hybrid was selected because it is easiest and most cheap to make. The interlayer hybrid consists of several different

layers with a single material and the performance of CFRTP are expected to be improved by replacing the part of fiber constituents by ductile fibers. By such combination, larger initial failure strain and a successive failure would be expected if the design of the configuration of carbon fiber and ductile fiber is proper in the hybrid structure. Zweben [6] attempted to study the tensile behavior of carbon/aramid hybrids, and developed two models: one to analyze the statistical failure mechanisms; the other to obtain hybrid strain concentration factors and ineffective length. In this report, the analysis predicted that high elongation fibers behaved like crack arrestors and the enhancement of failure strain depends on the ratio of stiffness both fibers.

There are various definitions for “hybrid effect”. The original definition of the hybrid effect is the apparent failure strain enhancement of the low elongation fibers in a hybrid composite [7]. The hybrid effect is influenced by several factors, such as volume fraction of both constituents, the mechanical property of two fibers, degree of dispersion, etc. Although some researchers believed increased dispersion of two fibers can obtain larger hybrid effects [8-9], with a finer fiber dispersion, damage to the high elongation fiber by the failure of low elongation fiber would be limited [10]. Jang et al. [11] also found that interlayer hybridization can enhance delamination under impact loading, which was found to be an effective energy absorbing process in hybrids. In addition to the hybrid effect, some hybrids show another positive influence. Their failure mode can be different from that of non-hybrid. In an interlayer hybrid, high elongation fibers keep load after low elongation fibers break and avoid abrupt and catastrophic failure, which is desirable because it leads to larger energy absorption and prevents sudden accidents.

In an attempt to reduce the cost, many researchers have selected glass as ductile fibers and combined them with carbon fibers. However, most of the glass fibers are not recyclable and they hopelessly lose their mechanical performance through the recycling process. On the contrary, aramid fibers, aromatic polyamide fibers with heat-resistance and strength, have as high performance as glass fibers with much lighter weight and they keep their performance, which makes aramid suited to be recycled and used for sustainable materials.

The main target of this research is to investigate the effect of the aramid layer in carbon/aramid hybrid in order to optimize the design of hybrids with a maximized hybrid effect and a reduced brittle failure. Furthermore, this research compares the potential of aramid and glass in the interlayer hybrid and disclose aramid is superior to glass in mechanical performance in addition to recyclability.

In this study, carbon fiber paper and aramid fiber cloth were used to manufacture interlayer carbon/aramid hybrid composites. The ratio of carbon fibers to aramid fibers is fixed as 1:1. Furthermore, carbon/glass fiber hybridized thermoplastic was manufactured with the same volume ratio and stacking sequence and compared with carbon/aramid fiber hybrids. The hybrid effect with different aramid fiber cloths were studied and compared with glass fiber through several types of loadings——tension, flexural, impact loadings.

2 MATERIALS AND PREPARATIONS

2.1 Materials

A type of discontinuous carbon fiber paper reinforced thermoplastics (CPT) sheet (Awa Paper Co. Ltd.) which is consist of Polyamide 6 (PA6) and 6mm-long discontinuous carbon fibers was used. CPT sheet was made by papermaking technology and the volume fraction of CPT was 20%. And the materials for hybridizing are two types of continuous aramid fiber cloths from Teijin Co. Ltd; M1000s and M0200s. M1000s has thicker bundle than M0200s, which is obvious from the surface of them in Figure 2 and the information of two aramid cloths is shown in Table 1. To achieve 1:1 volume ratio of carbon fiber and aramid fiber in hybrid materials, aramid cloths were piled up with PA6 films inserted between them. The interlaminar sequence design is carbon/aramid/carbon/aramid as shown in Figure 1, which is chosen based on the previous study. Continuous glass fiber fabric was also used to make hybrid with same condition as for comparison. Its thickness is 0.25mm and fiber volume fraction is 45%. The appearance of the glass fabric is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 1: The image of the interlayer hybrid structure

Figure 2: The appearance of two continuous aramid cloths

Name	Number of fibers [/inch]	Thickness [mm]
M0200s	34*34	0.11
M1000s	18*18	0.24

Table1: The information of aramid cloths

Figure 3: The appearance of continuous glass fabric

2-2 Manufacturing of hybrid composites

In this study, two kinds of carbon/aramid hybrids and one carbon/glass hybrid were made. These hybrids were stacked with the PA6 films inserted between them and made into plates through compression molding method. The detail stacking sequences are shown in Table 2. Before molding, they were put into the vacuum drying machine (DRV320DA, ADVANTEC, Japan). After that the sheets were placed onto the heating and cooling auto press (Pinette Emidecau Industries, France) and molded. The molding condition was shown in Figure 4. After the molding process, the hybrid plates were cut into the desired size specimens with the composite material cutting machine (AC-500F, MARUTO, Japan). In addition, pure carbon fiber or aramid fiber reinforced thermoplastics were also made under the same condition and they are named as CPT, Pure M0200s, Pure M1000s and Pure Glass.

	Name	Materials	Stacking sequence
Pure	CPT	CPT	C ₂₄
	Pure M0200s	CPT, M0200s	A ₁₆
	Pure M1000s	CPT, M1000s	A ₈
	Pure glass	CPT, Glass	G ₇
Hybrid	Hybrid M0200s	M0200s	[C ₈ /A ₄ /C ₄]s
	Hybrid M1000s	M1000s	[C ₈ /A ₂ /C ₄]s
	Hybrid glass	Glass	[C ₈ /G ₂ /C ₄]s

Table 2: The Information of stacking sequences

Figure 4: The molding condition

3 EXPERIMENTAL

In this study, four types of experiments were carried out: tensile test, three-point bending test, three-point impact test, and Izod impact test.

3.1 Tensile test

Tensile test was performed in accordance with the ASTM D 3039 standard to investigate tensile strength, tensile modulus, and failure strain. The dimension is 15 mm in width and 200 mm in length and the gauge length is 100 mm. 5 specimens were tested with the universal testing machine (AUTOGRAPH AG-Xplus, Shimazu, Japan).

According to these standards, the mechanical properties were calculated.

$$\sigma_t = \frac{P}{bh} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_t = \frac{\Delta l}{l} \quad (2)$$

$$E_t = \Delta\sigma_t / \Delta\varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

where, σ_t : Tensile stress, P : Tensile load, b : the width of specimen, h : the thickness of specimen, ε_t : Tensile strain, l : the length of specimen, ΔP : the difference of tensile load between two selected calculating points, $\Delta\delta$: the difference of deflection between two selected calculating points

3.2 Three-point bending test

Static three-point bending test was performed according to the ASTM D 790-03 standard to investigate the flexural strength, flexural modulus and flexural failure strain with the table-top precision universal tester (AUTOGRAPH AGS-X, Shimazu, Japan). The support span-to-depth ratio of 16:1 was chosen and the width is 15 mm. The load was applied at the middle of the span and the loading speed was 1mm/min. During the test, specimens were observed and photographed with the high-speed video camera (FASTCAM SA-X, PHTRON, Japan). The same video camera was also used in the impact tests. This experiment was carried out using 6 specimens.

According to these standards, the mechanical properties were calculated.

$$\sigma_b = \frac{3PL}{2bh^2} \quad (4)$$

$$\varepsilon_b = \frac{6\delta h}{L^2} \quad (5)$$

$$E_b = \frac{L^3}{4bh^3} \left(\frac{P}{\delta} \right) \quad (6)$$

where, σ_b : Flexural stress, P : Flexural load, L : Span between to supporters, b : the width of specimen, h : the thickness of specimen, ε_b : Flexure strain, δ : the deflection, E_b : Flexural modulus

3.3 Three-point impact test

Three-point impact test was conducted with the high-speed puncture impact tester (HITS-P10, Shimazu, Japan) to investigate the energy absorption ability and impact durability. The test was carried out based on the standard JIS K7084. The dimension and the number of specimens were the same as the static bending test.

According to this standard, the mechanical properties were calculated.

$$a = \frac{W}{hb} \quad (7)$$

where, a : Energy absorption, h : Thickness of specimen, b : Width of specimen

3.4 Izod impact test

Izod test was carried out with the instrumented pendulum impact tester (Instron USA, POE 2000e) following the testing standard of K7110 from JIS in order to investigate the mechanical performances against impact in a different way from Three-point impact test. The dimension is 52 mm in length and 10 mm in width. The energy absorption ability was calculated with the same equation as three-point bending test. The experiment was carried out using 8 specimens.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Tensile test

Tensile stress-strain curves are given in Figure 5. The pure aramid materials had more than two times higher failure strain than that of CPT, which implied aramid's outstanding toughness and durability. However, it also suggested that aramid had less stiffness and their tensile modulus were about half of CPT's. In general, there is a trade-off relation between stiffness and toughness and ideal hybrid structure would give the material both stiffness of carbon and toughness of aramid due to the hybrid effect working well. But in tensile test, the hybrids didn't show the disadvantages from aramid component because both two kinds of carbon/aramid hybrid composites broke at almost the same strain as that of CPT and behaved similarly. It would be because the strength of the aramid material is not enough. When the carbon fiber layer reached its failure strain and broke first, the aramid layer was barely able to sustain the whole stress and the catastrophic failure happened. This tendency was also true in the case of carbon/glass hybrid and all hybrid composites which shows a similar tendency as CPT does. If aramid's tensile strength was larger, the stress-strain curve in the hybrid would be extended. To sum up, hybrids don't bring the advantage of aramid fibers in terms of tensile property.

Figure 5: The stress-strain curves in tensile test

4.2 Three-point bending test

In Figure 6, the hybrid composites showed higher flexural strain than CPT, at a slight expense of flexural strength and flexural modulus. However, compared with CPT with a brittle load-displacement curve (Figure 7), they had satisfactory ductile behavior with several load drops after the first peak. This result suggested that the ductile fibers can reduce the risk of catastrophic failure, which can also be seen in the load-displacement curves (Figure 8) and the picture taken by a high-speed video camera (Figure 9), which indicates the tension failure takes place first with the bottom carbon fiber layer breaking. Comparing the three kinds of the hybrids, carbon/aramid hybrids, especially Hybrid M1000s showed more ductile than carbon/glass hybrid. It can be concluded that carbon/aramid improved the toughness of CPT successfully and it is more obvious in the hybrid with thicker bundles. Thick bundles would show better stress transfer and load sustainability, which made Hybrid M1000s the toughest material. Although the pure glass fiber composite has higher mechanical performance, the hybrid with glass cloth can't achieve the same ductile level in hybrid with aramid cloth, which can be seen from the lowest flexural strain in the first failure of the carbon/glass hybrid.

To maximize the reinforcement effect, the design of the hybrid was considered. There are three kinds of ways to make CPT tougher (Figure 10).

1. To raise the position of the curve after the first peak
2. To increase the modulus after the load drop
3. To keep the curve at a high position and extend the final destruction period.

The drop in the load-displacement curve occurs when the bottom carbon layer breaks. At this time, if carbon breaks with a large load applied to it, the upper layers bear the rest load, leading to a large load drop. Therefore, breaking the carbon layer at an early stage would be effective to suppress the subsequent load drop. As load-bearing performance is dependent on layer thickness, to reduce the thickness of the lowest carbon layer would be an effective method to realize the early break. The bending modulus in the laminate depends on the relative thickness of the carbon/aramid layer. Therefore, making the bottom layer thinner and the middle carbon thicker will increase the relative carbon thickness after the first peak, leading to improving the stiffness. In three-point bending test, a decrease in load happens along with the breakage of the carbon layers and the breakage occurs in the lower, upper and middle order. Therefore, the final breaking point can be extended by making the middle carbon layers thicker and improve load-bearing performance.

Figure 6: The flexural properties in three-point bending test

Figure 7: The load-displacement curves of CPT in three-point bending test

Figure 8: The load-displacement curves of the hybrids in three-point bending test

Figure 9: The failure mode of the hybrid composites in three-point bending test

Figure 10: The ideal failure behavior in three-point bending test

4.3 Three-point impact test

In three-point impact test, the energy absorption abilities were measured and the load-displacement curves are given as Figure 11. The results showed an improvement of the impact resistance in the hybrids and it was similar to that in the static three-point bending test where the hybrid also failed in steps. The hybrids absorbed larger energy than CPT and the effect was more obvious in the one with thicker aramid fabric. Hybrid M1000s absorbed more than six times higher energy than CPT, which can be seen in Figure 12. The several drops happened in the curves can be explained by the pictures taken by the high-speed camera (Figure 13). Similar to the static bending test, the middle layer with ductile fiber sustained the impacts after the bottom carbon layer broke. The glass hybrid showed the highest peak in the load-displacement curves due to better mechanical property but the aramid hybrids absorbed more energy than the glass hybrid thanks to the better impact resistance. Among them, Hybrid M1000s has the best energy absorption capacity. It can be concluded that the thick aramid fabric shows superiority in this kind of hybrid and can be further investigated in near future.

Figure 11: The load-displacement curves of the hybrids in three-point impact test

Figure 12: The information of energy absorption in three-point impact test

Figure 13: The failure mode of the hybrid composite in three-point impact test

4.4 Izod impact test

The result of Izod impact test was shown in Figure 14 where a similar tendency from the result of three-point impact test can be observed. Among them, Hybrid M1000s with a thick bundle showed the best impact resistance and absorbed more than twice as much energy as that of CPT. In this test, the failure stopping phenomenon can also be seen from the picture took with the high-speed camera shown in Figure 15 where tensile side carbon layer broke firstly and the delamination between the carbon layer and the middle layer happened, which would absorb the part of impact energy. Comparing three kinds of hybrids, aramid fabric, especially M1000s, shows better toughness improvement ability than glass fabric.

Figure 14: The information of energy absorption in Izod impact test

Figure 15: The failure mode of the hybrid composite in Izod impact test

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, continuous aramid and glass fiber fabrics were applied to the hybrid with discontinuous CFRTP and the hybrids were investigated through their tensile, flexural and energy absorption behaviors. From the results, several conclusions can be given.

- (1) In tensile test, the ductile fiber layer didn't bring its advantage in a hybrid where the hybrids and CPT show similar performance.
- (2) In the flexural and the dynamic tests, the hybrids with the aramid fiber can improve the toughness of CPT, which is expected to broaden the CFRTP application.
- (3) The hybrid effect is more obvious in impact loads than the static loads.
- (4) In this study, the hybrid with thick fiber bundles showed better performance and the bundle thickness can be an important parameter to control the mechanical performance.
- (5) Both two hybrids with aramid cloth show superior to the one with glass cloth, which indicates the aramid cloth can have more potential to be applied to CFRTP hybrid.
- (6) To maximize the reinforcement effect, further research about the lamination sequence and thickness of each layer should be carried out.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Part of this study has been conducted as the Japanese METI project "the Future Pioneering Projects / Innovative Structural Materials Project" since 2013fy. The authors would like to express sincere appreciation to the project members who have provided valuable information and useful discussion.

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